

Integration of Biotechnology Content knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The integration of biotechnology into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum offers a pathway to increase students' acquisition of essential 21st-century skills. This paper explored the rationale, challenges, and opportunities associated with incorporating biotechnology education into the curriculum to prepare students for the complexities of a globalized world. Biotechnology, at the intersection of biology and technology, held promise across diverse sectors such as healthcare, agriculture, and environmental conservation. The paper discussed the nature of Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum, emphasizing its thematic and spiral organization, and identified gaps where biotechnological topics were underrepresented. Challenges in implementation, including lack of qualified teachers, resource constraints, and ethical considerations, were explored. Opportunities, such as promoting practical, inquiry-based learning and promotion of interdisciplinary connections, were highlighted. The paper concluded that successful integration of biotechnology requires fundamental efforts to review secondary school biology curriculum. Thus, it suggested curriculum review, partnerships for access to biotechnology resources to facilitate instruction, and teachers' professional development.

Keywords: Biotechnology education, 21st-century skills, Secondary school, Biology curriculum

Introduction

In the 21st century, education systems worldwide face the challenge of preparing students for a rapidly evolving and increasingly complex global competitiveness. As societies transition towards knowledge-based economies, the acquisition of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, creativity, adaptability, and ethical awareness, has become imperative for students to thrive in a competitive and interconnected world (Isma'il & Cyril, 2022; Trilling & Fadel, 2008). In Nigeria, the education sector faces the challenge of adapting curriculum frameworks to meet the demands of the modern era and the country's socio-economic development goals. Aham et al. (2022) argue that teaching and learning have shifted towards equipping students with the skills to solve real-life problems they encounter daily, rather than solely focusing on classroom-based knowledge.

According to Bahri et al. (2014), biotechnology education promotes the acquisition of 21st century skills, which are key for the contemporary economy. For the nation to flourish in this century, there is a need for strategic priority to emphasize technologically infused topics in biology (Aham et al., 2022). Biotechnology, a field at the intersection of biology and technology, encompasses a wide range of applications that leverage living organisms or biological systems to develop products and processes beneficial to society. In recent years, biotechnology has emerged as a powerful tool with diverse applications in sectors such as healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and industrial manufacturing (Schmidt, 2023). Understanding the basics of biotechnology is essential for appreciating its significance and potential impact on various aspects of human life. As biotechnology continues to evolve, it is essential to stay informed about the latest developments and ethical considerations shaping the field's future.

As part of ongoing efforts to reform the educational system, there is a growing recognition of the need to integrate emerging fields such as biotechnology into the curriculum to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and competencies required for success in the 21st century (Okeke, 2019). Hiong and Osman (2013) have proven the possibility of integration of 21st century skills in biology education. Since the beginning of the 21st century, modern biotechnology has been integrated into senior secondary science curricula in numerous countries, including the United States, England, Canada, and New Zealand (Kooffreh et al., 2021; Nordqvist & Johansson, 2020). Biotechnology education incorporates aspects of ethics and morals, which are less frequently encountered in subjects like chemistry, physics, or other areas of biology (Nordqvist & Johansson, 2020). Biotechnology education often includes ethical, emotional, political, and social dimensions, setting it apart from many

other science natural science subjects. For example, while scientists generally agree that genetically modified food is safe, many people still have concerns or oppose their use (Nordqvist & Johansson, 2020).

Biotechnology is formed by combining biology and technology. It involves using microorganisms or biological substances to carry out particular manufacturing processes or industrial functions (Unoma & Menkiti, 2017). It is the application of biological knowledge and techniques to develop products and processes that improve human health, agriculture, industry, and the environment, holds immense promise as a catalyst for advancing education and driving innovation (UNESCO, 2015). By integrating biotechnology into the secondary school biology curriculum, teachers can engage students in hands-on learning experiences that not only deepen their understanding of biological concepts but also nurture the development of critical thinking skills and scientific inquiry (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023). Survey conducted in Nigeria by Unoma and Menkiti (2017) revealed that secondary school students exhibit a high level of unawareness regarding biotechnology products and services. Another study by Kooffreh et al. (2021) revealed that secondary school students generally demonstrated limited knowledge, perception, and interest in biotechnology.

These studies stand in contrast to the findings of Bahri et al. (2014) in Malaysia, where secondary school students were reported to possess a moderate level of knowledge, perception, and attitude towards biotechnology. Consequently, Unoma and Menkiti (2017) and Kooffreh et al. (2021) emphasized the need for integrating biotechnology into the current Nigerian senior secondary school biology curriculum, a step that has not yet been taken. The integration is essential for increasing students' understanding and appreciation of the benefits of biotechnology. Based on this background, this paper explores the rationale, challenges, and opportunities associated with integrating biotechnology into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum to advance 21st-century skills among students.

Curriculum is prearranged experiences that serve as a teacher's guide and often the sole resource used by teachers. It links educational goals and subject content with the act of teaching in the classroom, containing the syllabus and required subject content learned in the school system (Westbrook et al., 2013). A coherent curriculum has the greatest impact on student success and is the means through which the philosophy of education can be actualized. This implies that the curriculum encompasses all experiences to which learners are exposed under the guidance of the school. Essentially, the function of a curriculum includes everything that affects and influences a learner to be relevant and useful to their society. Parish (2013) contends that learning must be focused on the curriculum. Therefore, the biology curriculum is a key reference point for biology teachers and a vehicle for effective instruction. It encompasses required content learned in the school system.

Nigeria operates a federal system, and as a result, the Federal Ministry of Education, through National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) and with the inclusion of stakeholders, prepared the biology curriculum under which all senior secondary schools in Nigeria operate (Abe & Owoey, 2016). According to Isma'il and Matazu (2024), the biology subject is an essential part of the secondary school science curriculum, offering students an in-depth understanding of the living world. The current Nigerian Secondary School Biology Curriculum was adapted and revised from the 1985 edition developed by Comparative Education Study and Adaptation Centre (CESAC) under National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008). The objectives of the curriculum, derived from the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), The aims of the Nigerian senior secondary school biology curriculum are to prepare students to acquire:

1. Adequate laboratory and field skills in biology;
2. Meaningful and relevant knowledge in biology;
3. Ability to apply scientific knowledge to every day's life in matters of personal and community health and agriculture;
4. Reasonable and functional scientific attitude.

The biology syllabus, as contained in the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008) curriculum, is arranged spirally using a thematic approach (Oyovwi, 2021). The content and topics cover four major themes:

1. Organization of Life: This includes topics describing the basic structure and classification of living things, such as cell structure and functions.
2. Organisms at Work: This theme covers anatomy and physiological activities, including the digestive, respiratory, and nervous systems.
3. The Organism and its Environment: This theme explains the relationship between organisms and their environment, covering ecology and conservation.
4. Continuity of Life: This describes reproduction, genetics, and evolution.

These themes are directly relevant to secondary school students and society at large. The spiral and thematic arrangements ensure a gradual progression of learning concepts from concrete to abstract (Ogunkola & Samuel, 2011). The curriculum's spiral approach means that students study the same topics throughout their academic careers, with each encounter becoming more complex and reinforcing previous knowledge. The NERDC (2008) curriculum organizes its content into six

sectors: Topic, Performance Objectives, Content, Activity (Teacher and Students), Teaching and Learning Materials, and Evaluation Guide. This organization guides teachers in preparing the scheme of work and daily lesson plans.

The curriculum emphasizes field studies, guided discovery, laboratory techniques, and skills, along with conceptual thinking. The curriculum promotes student-centered instruction with a focus on experimentation, questioning, inquiry, discussion, and problem-solving, which are essential for students' comprehension (Aham et al., 2022; NERDC, 2008). However, explicit references to biotechnology topics are not prevalent within the curriculum.

Rationale for Integration of Biotechnology into Secondary School Biology Curriculum

The integration of biotechnology into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum holds significant importance in preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of the 21st century. By incorporating biotechnology into the curriculum, Nigerian secondary schools can equip students with the knowledge, skills, and mindset necessary to thrive in a rapidly evolving scientific world. One of the primary reasons for integrating biotechnology into the biology curriculum is to align education with real-world applications and industry demands.

Biotechnology plays a central role in various sectors, including healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and industrial manufacturing. By exposing students to basic biotechnological concepts and techniques, it will help in preparing students for future careers in biotechnology-related fields (Oyinloye, 2018). Moreover, integrating biotechnology into the curriculum nurtures critical thinking, problem-solving, and innovation skills among students. Biotechnological research and development require creativity, analytical thinking, and the ability to work collaboratively across disciplines. By engaging students in hands-on biotechnological experiments and projects, teachers can cultivate these essential skills and nurture a culture of scientific inquiry and discovery (Ajayi & Akinpelu, 2023).

Furthermore, incorporating biotechnology education enhances the attractiveness of biology as a subject and promotes student engagement and motivation. Traditional biology education often focuses on memorization of facts and concepts, which may not resonate with all students. By introducing cutting-edge topics such as gene editing, synthetic biology, and personalized medicine, teachers can capture students' interest and curiosity, inspiring them to explore the fascinating world of biotechnology (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023). Also, biotechnology education promotes ethical awareness and responsible citizenship among students. The ethical implications of biotechnological advancements, such as genetic engineering and cloning, raise complex moral and societal questions. By discussing these ethical dilemmas in the classroom, teachers can cultivate students' moral reasoning and encourage thoughtful reflection on the societal implications of biotechnology (Bello & Maude, 2019; Isma'il et al. 2021).

Furthermore, integrating biotechnology into the curriculum contributes to national development goals by building human capital and innovation-driven growth. In an increasingly globalized economy, countries that invest in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education gain a competitive edge in innovation and economic competitiveness. By equipping Nigerian students with biotechnological knowledge and skills, the country can harness its scientific talent to address local challenges and participate actively in the global biotechnology

Challenges in Implementing Biotechnology Content Knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education

Integrating biotechnology education into the secondary school biology curriculum presents various challenges that teachers and policymakers must address to ensure effective implementation and optimal learning outcomes. Biotechnology offers immense potential for preparing students with essential 21st-century skills, but several barriers hinder its seamless integration into the curriculum, some of which are discuss below:

Lack of qualified teachers with proficiency in biotechnology: Biotechnology is a complex and rapidly evolving field that requires specialized knowledge and skills to teach effectively. Many secondary school biology teachers may not have received adequate training or professional development in biotechnological concepts and techniques. Regarding this matter, Sodangi et al. (2022) argued that continuous professional development is essential for effective implementation of the science curriculum by teachers. In similar vein, Ajayi and Adeyemi (2022) noted that, without competent teachers, schools may struggle to deliver high-quality biotechnology education, limiting students' exposure to the field. Teachers who are not well-versed in biotechnology may not be able to effectively integrate new developments and technologies into their curriculum, thereby failing to prepare students for the demands of the 21st-century workforce.

Resource constraints: Resource constraint pose a significant barrier to implementing biotechnology education in secondary schools. Many schools in Nigeria lack the necessary laboratory facilities, equipment, and reagents needed to conduct

biotechnological experiments and demonstrations (Oyinloye, 2018). The cost of acquiring and maintaining biotechnology equipment can be prohibitive for schools with limited budgets, especially in rural or underserved areas. As a result, students may miss out on hands-on learning experiences essential for understanding biotechnological concepts.

Outdated curriculum and teaching materials: The biology curriculum in Nigerian secondary schools often prioritizes traditional topics while neglecting emerging areas such as gene editing, synthetic biology among others. This gap can hinder students from gaining up-to-date knowledge in biotechnology. More so, Adeyanju and Adeyemo (2023) highlighted that, textbooks and instructional materials may not always reflect the latest advancements, which can limit students' understanding of current biotechnological concepts (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023). The curriculum, although comprehensive in its traditional scope, does not adequately reflect the rapid advancements in biotechnology, making it imperative to update both the curriculum and teaching resources to ensure that students receive a modern and relevant biotechnology education.

Ethical considerations: Ethical considerations surrounding biotechnology present challenges for teachers and policymakers. Biotechnological advancements, such as genetic engineering and cloning, raise complex moral and societal questions that must be addressed responsibly in the classroom. However, according to Bello and Maude (2019; Isma'il et al. 2021), undertaking these ethical dilemmas can be challenging, particularly when cultural and religious beliefs influence perceptions of biotechnology. Hence, teachers must ensure that biotechnology education promotes ethical awareness and promotes critical thinking about the societal implications of biotechnological innovations.

Lack of awareness and appreciation for biotechnology: Lack of awareness and appreciation for biotechnology among stakeholders, including parents, students, and policymakers, poses a challenge to its implementation in the curriculum (Unoma & Menkiti, 2017; Kooffreh et al., 2021). Biotechnology is a relatively new and interdisciplinary field that may not receive sufficient recognition or support compared to traditional academic disciplines. Teachers must advocate for the importance of biotechnology education in preparing students for future careers and addressing societal challenges (Oladipo, 2023).

Opportunities in Implementing Biotechnology Content Knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Secondary school students represent the optimal demographic for cultivating fundamental knowledge in biotechnology, as they constitute the future potential to elevate a country to a high-income and developed status (Bahri et al., 2014). Therefore, the integration of biotechnology education into the secondary school biology curriculum presents numerous opportunities for enriching students' learning experiences, development of scientific literacy, and preparing them for future careers in science and technology. Biotechnology offers a wide range of opportunities for hands-on experimentation, interdisciplinary learning, and real-world applications in various fields. Bahri et al. (2014) argue that early exposure to proper biotechnology education is essential to enhance students' awareness of ethical issues related to biotechnology.

One significant opportunity of implementing biotechnology education is the promotion of practical, inquiry-based learning experiences for students. Biotechnology involves hands-on experimentation, data analysis, and problem-solving, providing students with opportunities to engage in authentic scientific inquiry and discovery. By conducting biotechnological experiments and projects, students develop critical thinking skills, scientific reasoning, and laboratory techniques essential for success in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) disciplines (Oyinloye, 2018). In addition, integrating biotechnology into the curriculum facilitates interdisciplinary learning by connecting biology with other scientific disciplines such as chemistry, physics, mathematics, and computer science. Biotechnology draws upon principles from various fields, including molecular biology, genetics, biochemistry, and bioinformatics, providing a holistic understanding of biological systems and their applications. By exploring the interdisciplinary nature of biotechnology, students develop a broader perspective on science and its role in addressing complex societal challenges (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023).

Furthermore, implementing biotechnology education in secondary schools creates pathways for career readiness and workforce development in emerging fields of biotechnology. Biotechnology is a rapidly growing industry with diverse career opportunities in research, healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and biomanufacturing. By exposing students to biotechnological concepts and techniques early in their education, schools can inspire interest and cultivate talent in biotechnology-related fields, addressing the growing demand for skilled professionals in the biotech sector (Ajayi & Adeyemi, 2022).

Integrating biotechnology into the curriculum enhances students' awareness and understanding of ethical, social, and environmental issues associated with biotechnological advancements (Kooffreh et al., 2021). Biotechnology raises complex ethical dilemmas related to genetic engineering, cloning, bioprospecting, and biosecurity, which require thoughtful consideration and informed decision-making. By engaging students in discussions and debates about these ethical

considerations, teachers can promote ethical awareness, empathy, and responsible citizenship among future leaders and innovators (Bello & Maude, 2019; Isma'il et al. 2021).

Moreover, implementing biotechnology education creates opportunities for collaboration and partnerships between educational institutions, industry stakeholders, and research organizations. Biotechnology companies, research institutions, and government agencies can serve as valuable resources for schools, providing expertise, mentorship, and access to cutting-edge technologies and facilities. Through collaborations with external partners, schools can enrich students' learning experiences, expose them to real-world applications of biotechnology, and inspire future career pathways in the biotech industry (Oladipo, 2023).

Advancing 21st Century Skills through Biotechnology Content Knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education

Developed countries have been incorporating 21st-century skills into their classrooms for some time, resulting in significant impacts on education (Ahmad & Ismail, 2023). In the 21st century, the integration of biotechnology into the biology curriculum presents a unique opportunity to advance students' acquisition of essential skills and competencies needed for success in a rapidly evolving world. The 21st century requires a workforce capable of respectful communication, critical reasoning, creative problem-solving, and collaboration from diverse perspectives to enhance industry quality (Ahmad & Ismail, 2023; Isma'il & Cyril, 2022; Oghenevwe, 2022). Alismail and McGuire (2015) note that the integration of these skills has become a fundamental component of education curricula globally. Therefore, it is important for students in Nigeria to be well acquainted with 21st-century skills right from secondary school to ensure they thrive in a rapidly evolving global economy and future career aspirations.

Integration of biotechnology into the Nigerian senior secondary school biology curriculum will help teachers prepare students for future professional endeavours while addressing 21st century challenges and opportunities. The integration facilitates the development of 21st century skills (see Table 1). These skills include critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, communication, creativity, innovation, adaptability, lifelong learning, ethical awareness, information literacy, technological literacy, and social responsibility, which are essential for preparing students for scientific challenges and opportunities in today's society. Ahmad and Ismail (2023) reported that engaging students in these skills improves their motivation toward learning.

Table 1: Integrable Biotechnology Concepts and 21st Century Skills

Biotechnology Concept	Curriculum Integration	Activities	Assessment	21st Century Skills
Basic Genetic Engineering	Include genetic engineering in topics like pest-resistant crops.	Problem-solving activities exploring genetic solutions to agricultural problems.	Case studies and problem-based learning assessments.	Critical Thinking, Problem-Solving, Technological Literacy
Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs) Cloning	Teach the creation, benefits, and ethical concerns of GMOs. Discuss basics of cloning with examples like plant cloning.	Group projects on GMO research. Hands-on experiments and ethical debates on cloning.	Group assignments assessing teamwork and presentation skills. Role-playing and simulations for critical thinking and ethical reasoning.	Collaboration, Communication, Ethical Awareness, Critical Thinking, Ethical Awareness, Social Responsibility
Bioremediation	Explain bioremediation using local environmental issues.	Collaborative projects on bioremediation strategies.	Group presentations and reports.	Collaboration, Problem-Solving, Social Responsibility
Fermentation	Teach the basics of fermentation and its uses in food and industry.	Simple fermentation experiments (e.g., making yogurt or bread).	Lab reports and practical demonstrations.	Practical Skills, Critical Thinking, Innovation

Ethical Discussions	Incorporate ethical discussions into each biotechnology topic.	Classroom debates on genetic modification and biotechnology ethics.	Essays and debates for ethical reasoning.	Ethical Awareness, Responsibility
Introduction to Biotechnology	Focus on the evolving nature of biotechnology.	Update students with recent advancements through articles and research.	Assess integration of new information into learning.	Adaptability, Lifelong Learning, Information Literacy

Source: Author, 2024

Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving: Biotechnology education encourages students to think critically, analyze data, and solve complex problems through inquiry-based learning approaches. By engaging in hands-on laboratory experiments, research projects, and case studies, students develop the ability to formulate hypotheses, design experiments, and evaluate evidence systematically (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023; Isma'il & Cyril, 2022). Biotechnological techniques such as DNA sequencing, genetic engineering, and bioinformatics provide real-world contexts for students to apply their critical thinking skills and address scientific challenges related to healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and bio-manufacturing.

Collaboration and Communication: According to Yusof et al. (2022), effective class activities rely heavily on communication and collaboration, signifying the critical importance of 21st century skills. Chiruguru (2020) describes collaboration as the ability of a group of students to effectively complete tasks, share responsibilities, and achieve a common goal. Biotechnology education promotes collaboration and communication skills by encouraging teamwork, interdisciplinary learning, and knowledge-sharing among students. Through group projects, laboratory exercises, and classroom discussions, students collaborate with peers, share ideas, and work towards common goals (Ajayi & Adeyemi, 2022). Collaborative learning experiences in biotechnology require students to communicate effectively, listen to diverse perspectives, and negotiate consensus, mirroring the collaborative nature of scientific research and innovation. By working collaboratively, students develop interpersonal skills, empathy, and cultural competence essential for success in diverse professional settings.

Creativity and Innovation: Biotechnology education nurtures students' creativity and innovation by encouraging them to explore novel solutions to scientific problems and societal challenges. By engaging in project-based learning, design thinking activities, and open-ended inquiries, students have the freedom to generate new ideas, experiment with different approaches, and take risks in their learning (Bello & Maude, 2019; Isma'il & Cyril, 2022). Biotechnological innovations such as gene editing technologies, synthetic biology, and personalized medicine inspire students to think creatively and envision the possibilities of biotechnology to address global issues such as disease prevention, food security, environmental sustainability, and renewable energy.

Adaptability and Resilience: Adaptability and Resilience involve adjusting behaviours, thinking, or attitudes, to fit in the current or future environments while respecting time, resources, and systems constraints (Hiong & Osman, 2013). Biotechnology education cultivates adaptability and resilience skills by exposing students to the dynamic and evolving nature of scientific knowledge and technology. The rapid pace of biotechnological advancements requires students to embrace change, learn continuously, and adapt to new information and methodologies (Oyinloye., 2018). By experiencing uncertainties, setbacks, and failures in laboratory experiments and research projects, students develop resilience, perseverance, and a growth mindset that prepares them to thrive in a complex and unpredictable world.

Ethical and Social Responsibility: Social responsibility involves effectively managing technology and utilizing it in a manner that promotes the common good (Hiong & Osman, 2013). Biotechnology education instills ethical awareness and social responsibility in students by exploring the ethical, legal, and societal implications of biotechnological innovations. Students critically examine ethical dilemmas related to genetic engineering, cloning, gene editing, and bioprospecting, considering diverse perspectives and values (Bello & Maude, 2019). Through engagement with ethical issues in biotechnology, students cultivate empathy, integrity, and a sense of responsibility towards the ethical use of biotechnological advancements and their effects on individuals, communities, and the environment.

Conclusion

In the 21st century, the global education setting faces the challenge of equipping students with essential 21st century skills to thrive in a competitive and interconnected world. Biotechnology, with its diverse applications in healthcare, agriculture, and industry, represents a key area for integrating into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum. This integration not only increases students' understanding of biological concepts but also cultivates 21st century skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and ethical awareness. Overcoming the challenges and taking advantage of the opportunities

of biotechnology education, Nigeria can prepare students for future scientific challenges and opportunities in socio-economic development and sustainable growth in the country. Successful integration of biotechnology requires fundamental efforts to review secondary school biology curriculum and teacher training.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion

1. A review of the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum should be initiated to integrate biotechnology topics. This reform should prioritize updating content, introducing new biotechnological concepts, and ensuring alignment with 21st-century skills.
2. Partnerships between educational institutions, industry, research organizations, and government agencies should be encouraged. These partnerships can provide schools with access to resources, expertise, and career talk on biotechnological related issues.
3. There should be provision of training or professional development opportunities for biology teachers to improve their content knowledge and pedagogical skills in biotechnology instruction. This is necessary for effective teaching and learning of biotechnology concepts in relation to their real world applications.

References

- Abe, T. O., & Owoey, P. O. (2016). Teachers' perception of difficult topics in biology curriculum in secondary schools in Ondo State. *Journal of Research in Science Education*, 1(1), 114–127.
- Adeyanju, B. T., & Adeyemo, A. O. (2023). Biotechnology education in Nigerian. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 8(3), 102-113.
- Aham, A. C., Nwagbo, C. R., & Ibe, E. (2022). Instructional strategies for promoting genetics literacy for sustainable science education in the twenty-first century. *Journal of Educational Research on Children, Parents & Teachers*, 3(1), 583-594. <https://ercptjournal.org/>
- Ahmad, A., & Ismail, M. J. (2023). Effects of biology 21st-century teaching strategies on students' motivation. *Indonesian Journal of Educational Science and Technology (Nurture)*, 2(1), 15-28. <https://doi.org/10.55927/nurture.v2i1.2955>
- Ajayi, I. A., & Akinpelu, A. O. (2023). Enhancing students' performance in biology through biotechnology education in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 32(1), 45-58.
- Bahri, N. M., Suryawati, E., & Osman, K. (2014). Students' biotechnology literacy: The pillars of STEM education in Malaysia. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, 10(3), 195-207. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2014.1074a>
- Bello, I. Z., & Maude U. U. (2019). Promoting ethical awareness through biotechnology education in Nigerian secondary schools. *African Journal of Science Education*, 16(2), 145-159.
- Chiruguru, S. B. (2020). The essential skills of 21st century classroom (4Cs). Shingania University. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Suresh_Chiruguru2/publication/340066140_The_Essential_Skills_of_21st_Century_Classroom_4Cs/links/5e75277d4585157b9a4d9964/The-Essential-Skills-of-21st-Century-Classroom-4Cs.pdf
- Federal Republic of Nigerian (2013). National policy on education (6th Ed), Lagos; NERDC press.
- Hiong, L. C., & Osman, K. (2013). A conceptual framework for the integration of 21st century skills in biology education. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 6(16), 2976-2983. <https://doi.org/10.19026/rjaset.6.4121>
- Isma'il, A., & Cyril, M. (2022). The link between STEM education and technology transfer in fostering creativity and innovation. In *62nd Annual National Conference Proceedings of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria* (pp. 170-178).
- Isma'il, A., & Matazu, S. S. (2024). Identification of Perceived Difficult Topics in Senior Secondary School Biology Curriculum in Zamfara State. *Global Academic Journal Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 22-30. <https://doi.org/10.36348/gajhss.2024.v06i01.004>
- Isma'il, A., Bashir, S., & Abdulrahman, A. (2021). Ethics and strategies for its integration into science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) classrooms at secondary school level. In *61st Annual Conference Proceedings of the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria* (pp. 26-34).
- Kooffreh, M. E., Ikpeme, E. V., & Mgbado, T. I. (2021). Knowledge, perception, and interest regarding biotechnology among secondary school students in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education*, 49, 664–668. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bmb.21507>

- National Education Research and Development Council [NERDC]. (2008). *Senior secondary school curriculum: Biology for senior secondary schools 1-3*. NERDC Press.
- Nordqvist, O., & Johansson, S. (2020). Secondary school biology students' attitudes towards modern biotechnology characterised using structural equation modeling. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 16(2), em1822. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/115016>
- Oghenevwe, O. (2022). Biology Education in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges in the 21st Century. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361934056_Biology_Education_in_Nigeria_Issues_and_Challenges_in_the_21st_Century
- Ogunkola, B. J., & Samuel, D. (2011). Science Teachers' and Students' Perceived Difficult Topics in the Integrated Science Curriculum of Lower Secondary Schools in Barbados. *World Journal of Education*, 1(2), 17–29. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/wje.v1n2p17>
- Okeke, C. J. (2019). Curriculum Development and Implementation: A Review of Literature. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(22), 128-135.
- Oladipo, F. (2023). Building partnerships for biotechnology education: opportunities and strategies for Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Partnerships*, 15(3), 275-290.
- Oyinloye, G. O. (2018). Overcoming challenges in implementing biotechnology education in Nigerian schools: insights from teachers. *Journal of Biological Education*, 22(1), 89-104.
- Oyovwi, E. O. (2021). Effects of concept-mapping and inquiry strategies in teaching difficult curriculum concepts in biology on students' academic achievement and retention. *International Journal of Biosciences*, 18(6), 258–267. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/18.6.258-267>
- Parish, D. A. (2013). *The Impact of Professional Development on Student Achievement as Measured by Math and Science Curriculum-Based Assessments*. [Doctoral dissertation, University of North Texas].
- Schmidt, R. (2023). Biotechnology: current trends and future prospects. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 24(3), 155-167.
- Sodangi, U., Isma'il, A., & Abdulrahman A. (2022). Perception of secondary school science and mathematics teachers on Professional development participation in Zamfara State, Nigeria. *Integrity Journal of Education and Training*, 6(2), 37-45. <https://doi.org/10.31248/IJET2022.138>
- Trilling, B., & Fadel, C. (2008). *21st Century Skills: Learning for Life in Our Times*. John Wiley & Sons.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2015). Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering: Implications for the Development of Developing Countries. Retrieved from <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/biotechnology-effective-solutions-sustainable-development>
- Unoma, C. R., & Menkiti, B. U. (2017). The role of educational awareness of biotechnology products and services in senior secondary schools in Enugu East Local Government Area. *International Journal of Environment, Agriculture and Biotechnology (IJEAB)*, 2(3), 1192-1201. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijeab/2.3.24>
- Westbrook, J., Durrani, N., Brown, R., Orr, D., Pryor, J., Boddy, J., & Salv, F. (2013). *Pedagogy, Curriculum, Teaching Practices and Teacher Education in Developing Countries* (No. 2110; Issue December).
- Yusof, R., Ismail, J., & Radzi, A. M. (2022). Online Distance Learning: A New Learning Approach in the Malaysian Gifted Education System. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, 16(1), 28-46.